

Fabrication of 360 Degree Fire Protection System

Dhanush Krishnamurthy¹, Ranjith Kumar², Manoj R³, Manu R⁴, Dr Manjunatha G⁵

^{1 2 3 4} UG Students, School Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, India

⁵Assistant Professor, School Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, India

ABSTRACT

The 360-degree fire detection and suppression system is carried out using infrared flame sensors, temperature sensors and release valves of water sprinklers using IoT technology. The strategically placed sensors provide complete area coverage and continuously feed data to a central controller. Custom algorithms analyse this real-time data to identify threats and activate the nearest suppressant release valve once fire is detected. The IoT architecture allows quick coordination between sensors and suppressants to monitor the entire premises, detect ignition, track fire spread, and enable timely response to prevent infernos. Key features are 360-degree detection, real-time monitoring, intelligent threat analysis and emergency response automation to protect infrastructure against fire. The system provides complete coverage of the area to be protected against fire by utilizing infrared flame sensors and temperature sensors spaced strategically to avoid blind spots. The sensors continuously feed real-time data to a central controller via programming. Custom software algorithms analyse this sensory data to identify fire threats at the earliest. Once a possible ignition is detected, the system triggers alarms and suppresses the fire by activating release valves of the built-in water sprinklers or fire extinguishing agent nearest to the site of the fire. The IoT architecture ensures all components can communicate and coordinate efficiently to monitor the protected zone, detect fires, track their spread, and enable swift actuations to prevent large scale infernos. The project demonstrates how IoT technology can be leveraged to create smart, connected and robust fire protection systems that safeguard infrastructure, assets and human lives from fire accidents.

Keywords: IoT technology, 360 Degree, extinguishing, fire.

1. Introduction

Fire protection systems are critical for protecting people and property from the dangers of fire. A 360-degree fire protection system provides complete, protection to surrounding area by fire detection and suppression capabilities [1]. This type of system offers advantages over traditional directional or zone-based systems, including faster detection, pinpointed location identification, and rapid extinguishing of fires from all directions simultaneously. Fire protection is the study and practice of mitigating the unwanted effects of potentially destructive fires [2]. It involves the study of the behaviour, compartmentalisation, suppression and investigation of fire and its related emergencies, as well as the research and development, production, testing and application of mitigating systems [3]. Fire protection systems include fire barriers and their penetrations, fire detection alarms, and fire suppression systems. Fire protection systems can also include administrative practices to reduce fire frequency, such as good housekeeping, established fire watch for hot work, inspection and maintenance of plant equipment [4]. In this project we have made a prototype of automatic controlled 360-degree fire protection system which can control the fire without a help of man. Nowadays, machinery and robotic design become important in helping human [5]. This Fire Protection Robot was design to help people in any destructive burnt situation where this robot can extinguish burnt

area immediately using autonomous system. This autonomous system will be designed using programming and others additional circuit [6]. The primary objective of the 360 Degree Fire Protection System is to enhance the safety of both individuals and property by offering a proactive and automated approach to fire protection. Traditional fire suppression systems often rely on fixed fire-fighting equipment, which may not adequately cover all areas or respond swiftly to fire incidents [7]. The system's core functionality lies in its ability to detect fires using strategically placed sensors. Once a fire is detected, the system activates the corresponding dc motor, enabling it to rotate towards the fire source. The system to promptly respond to fires originating from any direction [8]. This control unit utilizes advanced algorithms to improve fire detection accuracy and optimize the operation of the dc motors [9]. A fire fighter robot is one that includes a miniature fire extinguisher. The automation extinguished fire by connecting a tiny fire extinguisher to the robot [10]. Active fire protection systems (sprinklers, heat and smoke detectors etc.) are designed to detect and control or extinguish fire in its initial stage and are more important from life safety perspective [11].

2. Literature

Dr. Arvind Mahalle et.al [12] presented the design and development of a 360-degree fire protection system to provide complete ceiling coverage for fire suppression. A key novelty is the use of a sprinkler head with 360-degree nozzle rotation. Uses a DC motor to rotate the sprinkler head via a gear system for 360-degree coverage and provides a practical design solution leveraging rotating nozzle concepts. S. Muruganantham et.al [13] used rotating nozzles for complete area coverage. The system is targeted for warehouses and large open indoor spaces. It uses a rotating nozzle assemblies mounted on a central elevated pipe. The central pipe contains water supply and electric cabling to nozzle assemblies. Entire system rotates at desired speed for full coverage water spray over protection area. Control unit with wireless connectivity can activate system remotely. Shirang Sandip et.al [14] presented microcontroller to control drive system, water pump, and nozzle rotation servo. And flame sensors are used to detect fire and ultrasound sensors to avoid obstacles. Water tank, pump and hose provide extinguishing capability. Robot can navigate to fire location and position itself for 360-degree extinguishing. Remote monitoring and control is possible through a Wi-Fi module. V.D. Yadav et.al [15] in this paper rotary spray nozzles are mounted on a central rotary shaft, driven by a motor. The spray nozzles are arranged to provide a 360-degree spray pattern. It provides complete fire protection coverage compared to fixed nozzle systems with limited spray angle. Rotary spray pattern allows using fewer nozzles for full coverage compared to fixed nozzles. Central motor shaft allows synchronized rotation of all nozzles. Rotation speed and flow rates can be controlled for optimized performance. Guru Prasad et.al [16] system used a flame sensor to detect fire and a microcontroller to control systems. Incorporates ultrasonic sensors and camera for navigation and water tank and pump to shoot water through nozzle to extinguish fire. Can be wirelessly controlled using a GUI from a remote base station. Mohd Aliff et.al [17] studied the key objectives are to detect fire threats and extinguish them quickly and safely. Uses a Pi microcontroller to control systems and Arduino for servo control. Incorporates a flame sensor and thermal camera for fire detection. Can navigate autonomously using ultrasonic sensors to avoid obstacles. Motorized hose nozzle rotates 180 degrees for wider fire suppression. Ayush Sarkar et.al [18] presented a 360-degree video analytics system to provide in-classroom training for firefighters using immersive virtual reality environments. Uses 360-degree cameras to capture training scenarios like burning buildings. Develops a CUDA-based machine learning model to detect fire, smoke and other hazards automatically. System is deployed on AWS cloud for easy access via VR headsets in classroom setups.

Dhamak Sagar et.al [19] utilized flame, heat and smoke sensors for fire detection. The key novelty is the 360-degree rotating mechanism for comprehensive monitoring. The system uses a water spray nozzle for fire extinguishing. The system incorporates IoT and mobile apps for remote monitoring and control. Xiaogeng Ren et.al [20] proposed a new intelligent fire detection system for green buildings that uses multi-information fusion technology. This allows the integration of different fire parameters from various sensors to improve fire detection accuracy. Traditional fire detection systems rely on single parameter sensors like smoke detectors or heat detectors. These can lead to false alarms or detection delays. Cong Zhang et.al [21] focused on analysing and evaluating fire safety systems for storage facilities handling dangerous chemicals. This is crucial for preventing and controlling fires with chemicals. Storage of flammable, explosive and toxic chemicals come with significant fire hazards if not properly managed. Venkatesh Kodur et.al [22] research exists on fire dynamics within enclosures and structural vulnerability at high temperatures. Evacuation response modelling helps set safety guidelines foregress. -Experiments assess fire resistance and suitability of construction materials. Integrated frameworks evaluate risk trade-offs between safety and efficiency. Sil vio bento da Silva et.al [23] focused on analysing fire statistics targets causal metrics, high-risk groups, fire dynamics simulations, material flammability experiments and suppression systems. Emerging work leverages AI on combined datasets. Areas needing focus include correlating socioeconomic factors with fire risk and improving global standardization for residential fire safety. Tanveer Rahman et.al [24] proposed an Internet of Things (IoT) based fire alarming and authentication system using Raspberry Pi 3. The system is designed for workhouses to provide fire safety and access control. It uses sensors like flame sensor, gas sensor, PIR sensor connected to a Raspberry Pi to detect fire and intruders. The system triggers an alarm and alerts residents via a mobile app upon detection. Dr Osamah Ibrahim Khalaf et.al [25] proposed an Internet of Things (IoT) based fire alarming and authentication system using Raspberry Pi 3. The system is designed for workhouses to provide fire safety and access control. It uses sensors like flame sensor, gas sensor, PIR sensor connected to a Raspberry Pi to detect fire and intruders. The system triggers an alarm and alerts residents via a mobile app upon detection. It also has an RFID based authentication system to control access to the workhouse using RFID tags and reader. M. Trinath Basu et.al [26] proposed an IoT-based forest fire detection system using sensors, microcontroller, and wireless communication. It uses temperature, humidity, smoke, and flame sensors to detect a forest fire. The data is processed by a Node MCU microcontroller. The system sends real-time alerts about a potential fire to the forest authorities via SMS and email using Wi-Fi.

3. Objectives

- To develop a robotic system capable of autonomously detecting and responding to fire hazards in warehouse.
- To implement flame sensors as a primary means of fire detection, ensuring the robot can accurately identify the presence of a fire.
- To utilize a microcontroller to process data collected from the flame sensors, enabling the robot to make informed decisions regarding the appropriate response to the identified fire hazard.

4. Methodology

The system uses a variety of sensors and components to manage the 360-degree fire protection system, and detection of fire. The system starts with a battery that supplies power to the entire system. An Arduino Uno, a microcontroller board, is the central processing unit that controls

the different parts of the system. A Flame sensor detects the level of heat in the atmosphere. When the heat level is high at a certain point, the sensor sends a signal to the Arduino Uno. The Arduino Uno then activates a water pump via a motor driver, which supplies water to the flamed area. The power supply module supplies power supply to the electrical components on the working model. The LCD displays the direction of the area where the fire is detected.

5. Prototype Model

Figure 1: System with Tank

Figure 2 : System With Nozzle

Figure 3: System With Microcontroller

5.1 Working of 360 degree fire protection system

- **Hardware setup:** Select appropriate motors and chassis for the robot, ensuring it can move in all directions. Install the motors, wheels, and any additional components onto the chassis. Mount the Arduino board securely onto the chassis. Connect the motors to the Arduino board, ensuring proper wiring and polarity. Attach the fire sensor(s) to the

robot, positioning them to detect flames from all directions. Connect the fire sensor(s) to the Arduino board.

- **Fire Detection Algorithm:** Develop an algorithm to read data from the fire sensor(s) and determine the presence of fire. Implement logic to trigger the robot's response when fire is detected, such as activating the extinguisher mechanism.
- **Movement Control:** Write code to control the movement of the robot using the motor drivers connected to the Arduino board. Implement algorithms for forward, backward, left, right, and rotational movements to enable 360-degree mobility.
- **Extinguisher Mechanism:** Design and implement a mechanism for dispensing fire extinguishing agent (e.g., foam or water). Integrate the extinguisher mechanism with the robot's chassis and ensure it can be activated remotely via the Arduino board.
- **Integration and Testing:** Integrate the fire detection algorithm, movement control, and extinguisher mechanism into a unified Arduino sketch. Test the robot's functionality in a controlled environment to ensure proper operation. Conduct simulated fire scenarios to evaluate the robot's ability to detect and extinguish fires from all direction.

5.2 Components of 360-Degree Fire Protection System

Figure 4: Components of Fire Protection System

6. Results and discussion

The model we have developed extinguishes the fire in the warehouse and used as safety purpose it detects fire for the range of 15cm and the Nozzle sprays the water at a speed of +2m to mitigate the fire inside the warehouse, the model moves automatically front and back using Arduino uno for controlling the system .The model carries a water storage tank with a capacity of 20l, motor driver, relay, power control Module are used to control the system and pump is used to pump the water from the tank to the nozzle.

7. Conclusion

The implementation of a 360-degree fire protection system is essential for ensuring comprehensive safety for warehouses and storeroom. By incorporating fire detection, suppression, and evacuation measures, this system provides a robust defence against potential fire hazards from all angles. Tailored solutions allow for the adaptation of the system to specific environments and hazards, optimizing effectiveness. With advanced fire detection technologies in place, the system can quickly identify fire threats, allowing for swift response and mitigation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank REVA University, school of Mechatronics Engineering for encouraging us to proceed with this project. We would also like to express our deep and sincere gratitude to our professor who guide us in this project, Dr.Manjunatha G, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, Bengaluru, for giving us the opportunity to do research and for providing invaluable guidance throughout this research. He as educated us the methodology to hold out the analysis and to present the analysis work as clearly as doable.

REFERENCE

- [1] Vikash Kumar, Singh Lakhan Singh, Automation in Fire Protection System Using Internet of Thing (IoT): July 2019.
- [2] Dr.Osamah Ibrahim Khalaf, Dr.Ghaida Muttashar Abdulsahib Noor Abdul Khaleq Zghair “IOT fire detection system using sensor with Arduino” August 2019.
- [3] Ahmed Imteaj; Tanveer Rahman; Muhammad Kamrul Hossain; Mohammed Shamsul Alam; Saad Ahmad Rahat ; “An IoT based fire alarming and authentication system for workhouse using Raspberry Pi 3 ” April 2017.
- [4] Ting L. Chien; H. Guo; Kuo L. Su; Sheng V. Shiau, “Develop a Multiple Interface Based Fire Fighting Robot” July 2007.
- [5] Md. Hazrat Ali*, Sultan Shamishev and Aidos Aitmaganbayev; “Development of a Network-based Autonomous Firefighting Robot”. June 2018.
- [6] Md. Rasheduzzaman, Abdul Awal, Asadulla Hil Gulib, S. M. G Mostafa; “Development and Implementation of Fire Fighting Robot” January 2017.
- [7] S. Sakthi Priyanka R. Sangeetha, S. Suvedha Ms. G. Vijayalakshmi; “Android Controlled Fire Fighting Robot” March 2017.
- [8] Joyal Raju; S Sheik Mohammed; Johaan Varkey Paul; Georgy Abel John; Dinanath S. Nair “Development and implementation of arduino microcontroller based dual mode fire extinguishing robot” March 2018.

- [9] Sunil Mathew¹, Gaikwad Sushanth¹, KR Vishnu¹, V. Vishnu Nair¹, and G. Vinoth Kumar² “Fabrication of Fire Fighting Robot” April 2016.
- [10] Nagesh MS¹, Deepika T V¹, Stafford Michahial¹, Dr M Shivakumar² “Fire Extinguishing Robot” December 2016.
- [11] Mukul Diwanji; Saurabh Hisvankar; Chhaya Khandelwal; “Autonomous Fire Detecting and Extinguishing Robot” January 2020.
- [12] Dr. Arvind Mahalle¹, Dr. Nakul Mahalle , Samyak Rasoni , Shubhayu Sarve, Pushkar Madamwar, Sachin Ballewar , “Design and development and of 360 degree and fire protection system .” June 2023.
- [13] S Muruganantham, T Arunkumar, K K Hariharasudan, S Sasi Kumar, S Jagadeesh, “Design and Fabrication of 360 Degree Fire Protection System.” June 2020.
- [14] Shrirang Sandip Panat, Parth Patil, Swapnil Joshi, David Gaikwad “Design and Development of a 360-degree Fire Extinguisher Robot using Microcontroller” May 2022.
- [15] Dhamak Sagar, Auti Mayur, Auti Iccha, Jore Tushar, “360 Degree Rotating Fire Protection System” May 2023.
- [16] L. Guruprasad, M. U. Yashwanth*, P. Vydyanath Prasad, B. V. Shreevara, Gangappa “Autonomous Fire Fighting Robot.” July 2020.
- [17] Mohd Aliff, MI Yusof, Azavitra Zainal “Development of Fire Fighting Robot (QRob).” April 2019.
- [18] Ayush Sarkar, Anh Nguyen, Zhisheng Yan, Klara Nahrstedt, “360-Degree Video Analytics Service for In-Classroom Fire fighter Training .” June 2021.
- [19] V. D. Yadav, Muskan A Mulani, Sanket D Deshmane, Shivam B Kalburgi Azaruddin S Attar, Akash A Dhumal “360 Degree Rotating Fire Protection System.” May 2023.
- [20] Xiaogeng Ren , Chunwang Li , Xiaojun Ma , Fuxiang Chen , Haoyu Wang , Ashutosh Sharma ,* , Gurjot Singh Gaba and MehediMasud, “Design of Multi-Information Fusion Based Intelligent Electrical Fire Detection System for Green Building.” March 2021.
- [21] Guo-Qiang Li, Chao Zhang, and Jian Jiang “Review on Fire Safety Engineering Key Issues for High-Rise Buildings”. December 2018.
- [22] Venkatesh Kodur and Puneet Kumar, Muhammad MasoodRafi “Fire hazard in buildings review, assessment andstrategies for improving fire safety". August 2019.
- [23]Sil Vio bento da silva , ROSARIA ON “An Analysis of Fire Safety in Residential Buildings through Fire Statistics.” July 2020.
- [24] Tanveer Rahman and Muhammad Kamrul “An IoT based Fire Alarming and Authentication System for Workhouse using Raspberry Pi” June 2020.
- [25] Dr.Osamah Ibrahim Khalaf Dr.Ghaida Muttashar Abdulsahib, Noor Abdul Khaleq Zghair, “IOT fire detection system using sensor with Arduino” August 2019.
- [26] M. Trinath Basu, Ragipati Karthik “IoT based forest fire detection system”. March 2018.